

AUTOMATED DETECTION AND CATEGORIZATION OF RIVER ISLETS USING SENTINEL 2 IMAGES

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ABSTRACT

Climate change and extreme weather events diversely affect riverine areas. Since decades river monitoring techniques in combination with satellite images, are used to draw meaningful conclusions about rivers e.g., river banklines, islets, flooded areas etc. However, the majority of the existing methods rely on manual techniques especially for the analysis of river islets. In this paper we propose an automatic method to find the islets of a river and analyze them. Firstly, the proposed method uses deep learning and GIS algorithms, applied on satellite images, to find the islets. Then, the detected islets are stored as GIS layers in multiple geometries i.e., polygons, lines and points. Finally, the created layers are used to classify the islets into the “missing”, “existing” and “new” ones resulting in an informative output for the users. In general, the proposed approach gives promising results and especially for the vectorization part which achieves an mIoU 94.9%.

Index Terms— river monitoring, islets detection, islets categorization, remote sensing, segmentation

1. INTRODUCTION

Inland waterways are highly dynamic environments affected by extreme weather events e.g., snowing, storms and drought. Nowadays, extreme weather events leading to natural disasters become increasingly common due to climate change. According to the European Union the consequences of extreme weather and climate-related events are devastating especially, for near river urban and rural areas [1]. At the same time, inland waterways constitute an integral part of citizens’ everyday life activities, for e.g., irrigation, transportation and tourism. From the Amazon in South America, Danube in Europe, Nile in Africa and Gange in Asia, river monitoring is an important application due to the socio-economic impact of rivers to the surrounding urban and rural areas. Although, the most common application for river monitoring is flood mapping, e.g., [2]–[4], due to the socio-economic impact of them, there are several other applications which are of great importance for river monitoring purposes, like riverside extraction, islets/char detection and mapping and drought monitoring. The river islets are commonly taken into account for several applications e.g., inland water

navigation and transportation, river monitoring and mapping among others. However, the dynamic environment of inland waterways makes the mapping of islets a demanding task. Hence the contribution of experts exploiting GIS software and satellite images, is required.

Since decades the scientific community utilize satellite images for river monitoring applications due to the temporal and rich information provided by them for any place on earth. Most of the river monitoring methods, e.g., those investigating and mapping river islets, propose a manual workflow in which they utilize satellite images timeseries in combination with GIS algorithms [5]–[9] to extract the desired information. Despite the high quality results, these methods have serious limitations such as the small monitoring area capability, the required expertise of the users and the human resources required in every application. Finally, the available manually annotated data about river islets are limited compared to other applications like flood mapping e.g., [10], [11]

In this paper we propose an automated approach for islets detection, vectorization and categorization along the entire length of rivers. Firstly, the WatNet and DeepWaterMap algorithms are used for inland water mapping because they are more robust than NDWI [12]–[14]. An advantage of the proposed method is the automatic vectorization of the islets using conventional GIS algorithms and the water maps. Finally, based on Land Cover Land Use (LULC) information the vectorized islets are classified into “new”, “missing” and “existing” creating an informative output for the user.

To sum up the contributions of the proposed method are:

- An automated approach for Islets detection and vectorization
- An automated approach which separates the detected Islets to the “missing”, “existing” and “new” ones over a specific time frame.
- The flexibility of the developed approach to be included into a holistic river monitoring system.

2. RELATED WORK

River monitoring is commonly conducted using a combination of earth observation and GIS techniques ([5], [6]). Hossain et. al. 2013 [5], analyze satellite images, spanning from 1973 to 2009, of the Gange River in

Bangladesh in order to extract meaningful information about river morphological changes e.g., banklines changes, erosion, accretion, vegetated islets area etc. The authors, processed the satellite images using two GIS software along with manually created vector data. A similar study was performed by Billah, 2018 [6] about Padma river, analyzing satellite images from 1975 to 2015. Ogilvie et. al. 2020 [7] compared threshold techniques in combination with MNDWI for mapping flooding areas, using data spanning from 1999 to 2019. Additionally, they investigated single sensor and multi sensor approaches, combining imagery from different satellite constellations e.g., Landsat 8, MODIS and Sentinel 2. Huque et. al. 2021 [8] described the methodology of river monitoring using remote sensing. In general, both static and dynamic characteristics of rivers could be monitored using only one satellite image or time-series respectively. In fact, the satellite images should be classified into “Water”, “Land” and “Sand”, commonly using image processing techniques. Finally, to assess the created classified images they mention a method which compare the pixel classes with the classes gathered by field work measurements approximately in the same date.

Virghileanu and Ioana-Toroimac, 2022 [15] proposed a monitoring technique for river islets, similar to the method presented in this paper, but they utilize spectral indices e.g., NDWI, instead of deep learning algorithms. Similarly to [15] Hossen and Sultana 2023 [16] proposed a method for shoreline change detection which uses a variety of software e.g., ArcGIS, ENVI etc. and the NDWI index. Also Hu and Wang 2022 [17] proposed a coastline monitoring approach which uses NDWI in combination with Otsu thresholding [18] and Canny Edge detector [19]. To sum up, deep learning inland water mapping algorithms are more robust compared to NDWI, especially using images with high cloud cover percentage [12], [13], [20].

To conclude, there are several river monitoring systems, which include an islet mapping manual procedure, with great results and with an in-depth analysis of rivers’ characteristics. However, the described manual methods are time consuming, they require experts during the river monitoring procedure or are directly dependent on existing software and use spectral indices e.g. NDWI and NDVI into their workflow. The proposed method aims to reduce the manual operation time of expert users, by gathering deep learning features and applying geospatial algorithms in an automated manner for islets detection and categorization, resulting in an informative output for the users.

3. METHODOLOGY

The proposed method has two parts the (i) Islets Detection and Vectorization (IDV) and the (ii) Islets Categorization (IC). Firstly, it uses two state-of-the-art inland water mapping algorithms i.e., WatNet [12] and DeepWaterMap [13], [20] to create water maps for the area of interest. To be more specific, WatNet is an encoder-decoder architecture which utilizes the MobileNetV2 [21] and DeepLabV3+ [22].

DeepWaterMap is an encoder-decoder architecture with convolutional layers, skip connections, batch normalization [23] and ReLU. Firstly, Sentinel 2 L2A images are downloaded for the monitoring area. From each satellite image the 2, 3, 4 and 8, (10x10m) and the 11, and 12, (20x20m) bands are combined to create 6-bands inference images, as the authors of DeepWaterMap and WatNet algorithms, suggest. The inference images are passed into the water mapping workflow which outputs either a binary or a grayscale water map for each inference image. Finally, the water maps are used as input to an automated GIS workflow which exports the (i) multi-point, (ii) multi-polygon and (iii) multi-line, GIS layers (.gpkg). Each layer includes a registration for each detected islet which are further classified into three classes. In fact, the proposed algorithm combines the information extracted from the inland water maps with conventional GIS algorithms like raster vectorization, lines to polygons conversion and polygons center point calculation, to automatically detect and vectorize the islets of rivers. The created inland water maps, using the developed workflow, of a part of the Danube River are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Water mapping algorithms applied to Sentinel 2 images. Water Maps: True Color Image (1st Row), WatNet architecture (2nd Row), DeepWaterMap (3rd Row). Zoom to the area of the red rectangle (2nd Column).

3.1. Islets Detection and Vectorization (IDV)

First and foremost, the created water maps, which have 10x10m spatial resolution, are passed into automated raster polygonization. Hereafter, each water map is accompanied with a set of vector shapes. The extracted shapes are passed into a filtering step which filters out the outliers based on the polygons’ area. If the shape is a water area, it is labelled with 255, otherwise it is labelled with 0. In fact, islets are small

areas, labelled with 0, which are surrounded by areas labelled with 1. Hence, the polygons representing the islets are separated from all the rest and stored as a “.gpkg” file. Finally, the polygon shapes are transformed into line shapes and the central point of each polygon is calculated. Both the lines and the points are stored in different files. Figure 2 presents the vector layers i.e., polygons, lines and points, created using the proposed approach for two inference images resulting to the detected islets. The flowchart of the presented method is depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 2: The created polygons, lines and points using the proposed method.

Figure 3: Islets detection and vectorization flowchart.

3.2. Islets Categorization (IC)

After the detection and vectorization of the islets, the proposed approach uses the Copernicus scene classification product, to classify them into the “missing”, “existing” and

“new” ones, providing to the user an informative output for river monitoring purposes.

First and foremost, this module uses a time series of Sentinel 2 L2A product images for the monitoring area. Then the user specifies the “base” image which is used as reference to the normal condition of the river. Afterwards, each image in the timeseries is compared to the reference image to find the pixels which changed from “water” to “land”. More concretely, the water map created for the base image and the Copernicus Scene Classification product of the image under process are compared to produce a change map, which indicates the pixels changed from “Water” to “Land” i.e., triggered pixels. Finally, the islets are categorized into “missing”, “existing” and “new” ones based on the triggered pixels inside each islet vector. If the number of triggered pixels divided by the total number of pixels, inside the islet polygon, is less than a threshold the islet is classified as “existing” otherwise it is classified as “new”, “missing” are the islets presented in a previous image but are not presented in the new one. The threshold value indicates the sensitivity of the module and by default is set to 0.5. Figure 4 presents an example of the existing (rows 1 – 3) and the created (4 – 5) products used for the islets’ categorization workflow.

Figure 4: Islets Categorization to “missing”, “existing” and “new”. An example of a “new” (red circle) and “existing” (red arrows) islets.

4. DISCUSSION

The proposed method is decomposed into two submodules i.e., Islets Detection and Vectorization (IDV) and Islets Categorization (IC) and consequently it will be evaluated separately. Firstly, the proposed method can easily adopt new water mapping techniques and thus follow the progress in the field. The limitation of IDV is the presence of False Positives (FP) islets especially at the edges of the images (Red Rectangle Figure 4). The included filtering technique filters out the FPs based only on their area and thus the FPs which are near the edges of the image and the water regions, are misclassified as islets due to their small area value. In future a rule will added into the workflow that will only keep the segmented regions that are surrounded by water and not by the edges of the image, to solve this issue. Additionally, the presence of clouds in the optical satellite images result in reduced quality of both the raster and vector products. Our approach is more robust to clouds because it uses state-of-the-art deep learning algorithms for inland water mapping instead of spectral indices e.g., NDWI.

Furthermore, to quantify the success of the vectorization process a set of 15 manual annotated islets were created. The goal of this comparison is to extract a safe conclusion about the vectorization part and not the detection i.e., how well we vectorize the correctly detected islets. Thus, the IoU [24] metric for each islet was calculated. To be more specific, the IoU values were span from 71% to 97% while the mIoU was 94.9 %. Figure 5 depicts an example of manually annotated islets (column 1) and the predicted masks using the proposed method (column 2).

Figure 5: Evaluation of Vectorization Process

The smallest IoU values were observed for the smallest islets, which is to be expected. Although the promising results of the vectorization procedure, the detection procedure could not be evaluated quantitatively due to the small amount of fully annotated data i.e., of satellite images in which every islet is manually annotated, which is tedious. In future, a dataset of annotated islets will be created using the proposed method

and by deleting the presented FPs. However, a qualitative test of the proposed method is presented in Figure 2 which also gives promising results.

Table 1: Intersection over Union (IoU) of 8 of the 15 images and the mean Intersection over Union (mIoU)

Image	1	2	3	4	mIoU (%) (15 mages)
IoU (%)	78.60	92.06	93.31	94.37	
Image	5	6	7	8	
IoU (%)	71.54	91.27	97.54	96.91	

Regarding the islets categorization module, state-of-the-art Land Use Land Cover algorithms should be included to replace the Scene Classification (SCL) product, and hence to utilize 10m GSD LULC information for Sentinel 2 images. Additionally, other alerts e.g., about erosion and accretion could be included in this module. Furthermore, a more sophisticated threshold value could be investigated exploiting more LULC classes for example the “Sand” and “Vegetation”. To conclude, the presented method achieves great results which ensure an improvement in existing river monitoring approaches.

5. CONCLUSION

Often, the extraction of informative conclusions using river monitoring techniques includes the manual intervention of experts. In this paper, we propose an automatic method for islets detection, vectorization and categorization providing a useful product for the experts and aiming to reduce their manual contribution in river monitoring. To be more specific, the developed method exploits existing surface water mapping deep learning techniques and GIS algorithms in combination with Land Use Land Cover information to firstly detect and then categorize river islets, into “missing”, “existing”, and “new” providing an informative output for the user. In the future, we will exploit the promising results of the presented approach to investigate new methods e.g., for riverbank lines extraction shoreline extraction, riverbank erosion and accretion estimation in order to create a holistic river monitoring system.

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